

African Red Slip Ware

Additional Iconography Catalogue

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*In an extreme view, the world can be seen as
only connections, nothing else.*

—Sir Tim Berners-Lee

1 Background

The iconography of the decoration on so-called African Red Slip Ware (ARS) is pivotal to understanding Late Antique iconology. The collaborative project between i3mainz and the RGZM presents this artefact category in an innovative and sustainable way through 3D digitisation. Characteristic of the North African bowls, plates and jugs are their pictorial decorations applied mainly by appliqués and stamps. As mass-produced image carriers and everyday objects, the ARS spread throughout the empire. The range of motifs includes mythological scenes as well as scenes from the Old and New Testament, circus, arena and hunting scenes as well as fish and plant motifs. The appliqué-decorated pottery thus provides insights into Late Antique imagination and its changes, as well as into the economic history of the period between the 3rd and 5th centuries AD in North Africa. Previous documentation methods were not able to capture the objects and their decoration in an adequate way. The digital recording of the RGZM's collections by 3D scans allows to compare potentially identical appliqués and to assign them to their negative forms and the corresponding stamps. Whereas vessel curvature previously falsified the assignment of appliqués and models, 3D analysis and visualisation tools now allow a comparison. Metadata created for each object increases the effectiveness and accuracy of determining image context and content. Issues related to the production of the ARS and the process flows within the workshops can be investigated through the analysis of the 3D data.

2 Overview

The following list shows the possible categories:

- A: Animal
- B: Human
- C: Mythological or Religious Character
- D: Ornament
- E: Plant
- F: Clothing
- G: Physical Item
- H: Architectural Element
- I: Profession
- J: Furnishing and Equipment
- K: Ancient Weapons
- L: Ceremonial Item
- M: Hybrid
- N: Human Part
- O: Musical Instrument

3 G: Physical Item

G / FT I Q111370381

This figure type shows a boating ship and can be found on "dish with boat and hybrids (O.40534)¹".

¹ars3do:5531692d-df51-407f-abf5-3d206d2be3a2

3 G: *Physical Item*

Figure 3.1: boat on dish with boat and hybrids (O.40534) [CC BY-SA 4.0 ARS3D Project, RGZM, i3mainz, J. Veller, L. Raddatz, F. Thiery, L. Rokohl]

3 G: *Physical Item*

G / FT II Q111372289

This figure type shows a boating ship and can be found on "bowl with erots on board (O.42130)²".

²ars3do:c833a181-6d1d-49be-8cb9-7b87c3f0f0b1

3 G: *Physical Item*

Figure 3.2: boat on bowl with erots on board (O.42130) [CC BY-SA 4.0 ARS3D Project, RGZM, i3mainz, J. Veller, L. Raddatz, F. Thiery, L. Rokohl]

G / FT III Q111372294

This figure type shows a boating ship with erots which are looking to the left, are naked and winged and reaching out the left arm to the left, and can be found on "bowl with erots on board (O.42130)³".

³ars3do:d11018cf-0c89-42f3-b543-07c8aa52fdfa

Figure 3.3: boat on mould erots on board (O.41418) [CC BY-SA 4.0 ARS3D Project, RGZM, i3mainz, J. Veller, L. Rad-datz, F. Thiery, L. Rokohl]

3 G: *Physical Item*

Figure 3.4: boat on mould erots on board (O.41418) [CC BY-SA 4.0 ARS3D Project, RGZM, i3mainz, J. Veller, L. Rad-datz, F. Thiery, L. Rokohl]

4 M: Hybrid

M / FT I Q111372221

This figure type shows a humoan-horse hybrid, looking to the left, standing and carrying a mantle and can be found two times on "dish with boat and hybrids (O.40534)¹".

¹ars3do:5531692d-df51-407f-abf5-3d206d2be3a2

4 *M: Hybrid*

Figure 4.1: human-horse hybrid 1 on dish with boat and hybrids (O.40534) [CC BY-SA 4.0 ARS3D Project, RGZM, i3mainz, J. Veller, L. Raddatz, F. Thiery, L. Rokohl]

4 M: Hybrid

Figure 4.2: human-horse hybrid 2 on dish with boat and hybrids (O.40534) [CC BY-SA 4.0 ARS3D Project, RGZM, i3mainz, J. Veller, L. Raddatz, F. Thiery, L. Rokohl]

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